

1 **Control of Xist by BRCA1.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We previously demonstrated control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation
7 in humans with two X chromosomes (females), Xist, by the two major cellular tumor suppressors, p53 and
8 Rb1 (1, 2), and demonstrated that activation of Xist occurs in females with breast cancer (3) and in males
9 with lung cancer (4), finding that aberrant Xist modulation occurs in human solid tissue transformation
10 (cancer) and demonstrating a mechanism for this (1-2, 5). We next discovered control of Xist by the
11 p53-associated molecule 53bp1 (6). 53bp1 has functions in DNA damage repair signaling (7-11)
12 suggesting Xist activation is linked to DNA damage and/or DNA repair. We demonstrate here control of
13 the non-coding RNA of *Xist* by the DNA repair associated BRCA1 (12-14). Thus, here, we discover
14 linkage between a major susceptibility gene for cancer in humans, *BRCA1*, which possesses functions in
15 cell cycle control and repair of damaged DNA, and expression of Xist.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

We discovered Xist activation and repression as a feature of transformation in humans by studying whole transcription in p53-sufficient and p53-deficient breast cancer cell lines (1). Xist was among the largest transcriptional differences transcriptome-wide. We then demonstrated that deletion of p53 was sufficient to drive activation of Xist *in vivo* in a genetically engineered model of p53 deletion-induced breast cancer (1).

Here, we studied the genetic determinants of Xist activation in human cells.

We measured total transcription in cultured human breast cancer cells (cell line MCF7) following *in vitro* depletion of BRCA1 messenger RNA using small interfering RNA (siRNA) (15).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
204531_s_at	0.069133	2.6376439	-3.749	0.7885806	BRCA1	3935/54675	92.8
235446_at	0.013424	-4.7754584	-2.325	-2.4606879	XIST	1088/54675	98.0

Depletion of BRCA1 was sufficient to result in activation of Xist transcription (Figure 1). MCF7 is a transformed breast cancer cell line.

We also measured total transcription in BRCA1-depleted immortalized but non-transformed MCF10A mammary epithelial cells *in vitro* (Figure 2) (16).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
204531_s_at	0.004962	6.60	-1.34592	3.03	BRCA1	704/54675	98.7
235446_at	0.089238	-2.37	-4.24672	-6.02e-01	XIST	7048/54675	87.1

Depletion of BRCA1 in MCF10A human mammary epithelial cells similarly resulted in activation of Xist transcription (Figure 2).

Discussion

We demonstrated here that BRCA1 is a genetic determinant for Xist activation and repression in human cells, suggesting DNA repair is intimately involved with the process by which Xist transcription is modulated during transformation. If p53 is intrinsically linked with Xist modulation in a cell- and tissue-type specific fashion, it will be increasingly difficult to separate transcriptional effects of p53 and Xist without enhanced attention.

References

1. Mamoor, S. 2023. The tumor suppressor p53 regulates Xist expression in certain cellular contexts.
2. Mamoor, S. 2023. The non-coding RNA Xist is activated by loss or mutation of the retinoblastoma tumor suppressor.
3. Mamoor, S. 2024. Xist is differentially expressed in human breast cancer and its expression is controlled by estrogen.
4. Mamoor, S. 2024. Xist is active in non-small cell lung cancer in humans.
5. Mamoor, S. 2023. Males and females activate Xist differently during solid tumorigenesis *in vivo*.
6. Mamoor, S. 2024. Control of Xist by 53bp1.
7. Callen, E., Di Virgilio, M., Kruhlak, M.J., Nieto-Soler, M., Wong, N., Chen, H.T., Faryabi, R.B., Polato, F., Santos, M., Starnes, L.M. and Wesemann, D.R., 2013. 53BP1 mediates productive and mutagenic DNA repair through distinct phosphoprotein interactions. *Cell*, 153(6), pp.1266-1280.
8. Noordermeer, S.M., Adam, S., Setiaputra, D., Barazas, M., Pettitt, S.J., Ling, A.K., Olivieri, M., Álvarez-Quilón, A., Moatti, N., Zimmermann, M. and Annunziato, S., 2018. The shieldin complex mediates 53BP1-dependent DNA repair. *Nature*, 560(7716), pp.117-121.
9. Cuella-Martin, R., Oliveira, C., Lockstone, H.E., Snellenberg, S., Grolmusova, N. and Chapman, J.R., 2016. 53BP1 integrates DNA repair and p53-dependent cell fate decisions via distinct mechanisms. *Molecular cell*, 64(1), pp.51-64.
10. Panier, S. and Boulton, S.J., 2014. Double-strand break repair: 53BP1 comes into focus. *Nature reviews Molecular cell biology*, 15(1), pp.7-18.
11. Ochs, F., Somyajit, K., Altmeyer, M., Rask, M.B., Lukas, J. and Lukas, C., 2016. 53BP1 fosters fidelity of homology-directed DNA repair. *Nature structural & molecular biology*, 23(8), pp.714-721.
12. Ganesan, S., Silver, D.P., Greenberg, R.A., Avni, D., Drapkin, R., Miron, A., Mok, S.C., Randrianarison, V., Brodie, S., Salstrom, J. and Rasmussen, T.P., 2002. BRCA1 supports XIST RNA concentration on the inactive X chromosome. *Cell*, 111(3), pp.393-405.
13. Xiao, C., Sharp, J.A., Kawahara, M., Davalos, A.R., Difilippantonio, M.J., Hu, Y., Li, W., Cao, L., Buetow, K., Ried, T. and Chadwick, B.P., 2007. The XIST noncoding RNA functions independently of BRCA1 in X inactivation. *Cell*, 128(5), pp.977-989.
14. Moynahan, M.E., Chiu, J.W., Koller, B.H. and Jasin, M., 1999. Brca1 controls homology-directed DNA repair. *Molecular cell*, 4(4), pp.511-518.
15. Dacheux, E., Vincent, A., Nazaret, N., Combet, C., Wierinckx, A., Mazoyer, S., Diaz, J.J., Lachuer, J. and Venezia, N.D., 2013. BRCA1-dependent translational regulation in breast cancer cells. *PloS one*, 8(6), p.e67313.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

16. Furuta, S., Wang, J.M., Wei, S., Jeng, Y.M., Jiang, X., Gu, B., Chen, P.L., Eva, Y.H.L. and Lee, W.H., 2006. Removal of BRCA1/CtIP/ZBRK1 repressor complex on ANG1 promoter leads to accelerated mammary tumor growth contributed by prominent vasculature. *Cancer cell*, 10(1), pp.13-24.